

The Bio-Eco rock development

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ABSTRACT

The extraction of natural rock for construction has caused severe environmental impacts, while the accumulation of agro-waste continues to pose ecological risks due to open burning and landfilling. To mitigate these problems, this study presents the Bio-Eco Rock Development (BERD), an upcycled green composite material composed of 40 wt% agro-waste, 50 wt% polyester resin, 10 wt% calcium carbonate, and a catalyst. BERD was designed to be lightweight, durable, and visually appealing. Mechanical property tests revealed that BERD reinforced with scrap wood exhibits the highest tensile strength (15.20 MPa), impact resistance (1394.94 J/m²), and flexural strength (40.24 MPa), making it suitable for structural and load-bearing applications. Moreover, macadamia nutshells and tea leaves improved flame resistance due to their inherent lignin and tannin content, respectively. These results suggest BERD's high potential as a sustainable alternative to natural rock in applications such as countertops, flooring, and wall panels. Given its strength, fire resistance, and eco-friendly composition, BERD is recommended for implementation in green building materials, especially in regions facing both stone mining-related pollution and agricultural waste surplus. The adoption of BERD can promote circular economy practices by transforming agro-waste into value-added construction materials.

KEYWORDS: Agro-waste, Environmentally friendly materials, Synthetic rock, Upcycled green composite material

1. INTRODUCTION

Agricultural waste (agro-waste) makes up a significant portion of global waste, and its disposal through incineration and landfilling poses serious environmental consequences.¹ Common disposal methods like burning and landfilling release pollutants into the air and soil, contributing to climate change and ecosystem damage. At the same time, pollution from natural stone mining—especially in limestone-rich areas—has become another pressing environmental issue worldwide.²

In Thailand, the agricultural industry produces large quantities of waste, including rice husks, straw, and sugarcane bagasse. These issues have severe environmental and public health implications. Traditionally, farmers have disposed of this waste through open-field burning, which releases harmful pollutants such as particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) and greenhouse gases, exacerbating air pollution and contributing to climate change.³ Agricultural burning in Thailand is a major source of PM_{2.5} pollution, responsible for over 2 million hospital visits annually, particularly for respiratory diseases.⁴

Approximately 83% of the country's crop residue burning is attributed to rice, maize, and sugarcane, highlighting the urgent need for sustainable alternatives.⁵ Additionally, the use of landfills for agro-waste generates leachate, a toxic liquid that seeps into the ground and contaminates water sources, posing risks to ecosystems and human health.¹ Improper waste management significantly affects climate change, resource depletion, and ecosystem health. The abandonment of agricultural residues may lead to the release of methane and carbon dioxide, exacerbating global warming.¹

Stone mining industry in Thailand, particularly in Saraburi Province, has long been a major source of environmental pollution. Limestone quarrying involves heavy blasting and crushing, which release massive amounts of fine dust (PM10) into the air.² Studies have found that PM10 levels in this region frequently exceed safe limits, increasing the risk of respiratory diseases for nearby communities.² Beyond air pollution, mining also leads to deforestation, soil erosion, and habitat destruction. Stripping land for quarrying eliminates vegetation that stabilizes the soil, making the area more vulnerable to landslides and other natural disasters. In addition, the environmental impacts of limestone mining include groundwater contamination, disrupted groundwater supply, energy and fossil fuel usage, reduced biodiversity, and dust pollution.

A number of studies have demonstrated the potential of agricultural by-products as reinforcement materials in composite development. For example, there was a study that reported incorporating jute and coir fibers into polymer matrices enhanced both flexural strength and water resistance, making them suitable for non-structural applications.⁶ Similarly, rice husk-reinforced polypropylene composites were found to exhibit favorable thermal stability and mechanical properties for interior paneling.⁷ Another investigation emphasized the importance of matrix selection in maintaining the environmental durability of bio-based composites over time.⁸ Collectively, these findings support the feasibility of utilizing agro-waste in composite materials, although the final performance depends on factors such as fiber characteristics, surface treatment, and resin compatibility.

To ensure the practical use of these composites in engineering and industrial applications, it is essential to conduct mechanical property testing to verify their suitability for real-world conditions.⁹ These composite materials, derived from agricultural waste, are intended for use in artificial stone products such as countertops, flooring, and wall panels, where they will be subjected to various mechanical stresses.¹⁰ Without thorough testing, it would be difficult to determine whether these materials can withstand long-term use, heavy loads, and environmental changes.¹¹

In particular, tensile testing, impact testing, and flexural testing are critical for evaluating the material's strength, durability, and overall performance under different loading conditions.¹² Tensile testing helps assess whether the composite can endure forces that attempt to pull it apart, which is especially important in structural applications where expansion and contraction may occur.¹³ Impact testing determines the material's resistance to sudden forces, ensuring that it does not crack or shatter easily when subjected to accidental impacts, such as dropped objects in a kitchen or commercial space.¹⁴ Flexural testing evaluates the composite's ability to bear bending loads, which is crucial for applications where the material must support weight across unsupported spans, such as countertops and decorative panels.¹⁵

These environmental problems highlight the urgent need for better waste management and stricter mining regulations in Thailand. Sustainable practices like converting agro-waste into energy and compost could significantly reduce pollution while benefiting farmers. This study therefore aims to develop green composite materials by upcycling agro-waste and explore their potential applications in various industries, ultimately contributing to more sustainable production and consumption practices.

The present work offers a distinctive perspective by examining a range of agricultural waste materials within a unified composite system. While earlier studies have often focused on a single filler type, this research compares several agro-waste sources—namely scrap wood, macadamia nutshells, tea leaves, coffee chaff, and rice husks—and evaluates their effects on key performance characteristics.

Mechanical and flame resistance tests reveal how specific chemical constituents, such as lignin and tannin, influence material behavior. By conducting all evaluations under consistent conditions, the findings provide practical guidance for selecting and engineering agro-waste composites suitable for various structural and decorative applications.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Materials

To develop the green composite BERD, agro-waste materials such as coffee chaff, tea leaves, rice husks, macadamia nutshells, and scrap wood were used as sustainable alternatives to traditional stone mineral fillers. A thermosetting polymer resin (polyester resin, Eternal Resin Co., Ltd.) was used as the binding agent, providing strength and durability to the final product.

2.2 Raw Material Preparation

The process began with preparing the raw materials. First, the agro-waste fillers were sun-dried to reduce moisture content and improve compatibility with the polymer resin (Figure 1). Once dried, they were ground and sieved to achieve a uniform particle size, making them suitable for composite fabrication.

Figure 1. Preparing the raw materials– a) rice husks; b) scrap woods; c) macadamia nutshell.

2.3 Composite Fabrication (Thermosetting Polymer Process)

The composite was fabricated by homogeneously blending agro-waste particulate fillers with a thermosetting polymer resin to produce a consistent matrix. A pre-conditioned mold was prepared to define the geometry and dimensional specifications of the final composite. The resin-filler mixture was then introduced into the mold and uniformly distributed to minimize void formation and ensure structural integrity.

Subsequently, the mold was subjected to thermal curing in a convection oven at a controlled temperature of 60–70°C for 30 minutes. This curing step facilitated crosslinking of the thermosetting polymer matrix, enabling effective interfacial adhesion between the resin and the agro-waste fillers. Upon completion of the curing cycle, the composite was demolded and subjected to post-processing operations, including edge trimming and surface finishing, to achieve the desired mechanical tolerance and surface quality.

This fabrication methodology enables the substitution of conventional mineral fillers with sustainable agro-waste materials, yielding a structurally robust and environmentally favorable composite suitable for advanced material applications (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Thermosetting polymer process – a) mold preparation; b) mixing; c) matrix placement; d) pouring; e) curing or setting.

2.4 Material Properties Testing

Mechanical and chemical properties testing including tensile strength testing (MPa), impact strength testing (J/M²), flexural strength testing (MOR, MPa) and flame spread testing were performed. The tensile test was conducted on a standard dumbbell-shaped specimen according to ASTM D638 Type I using a universal testing machine (Tinius Olsen, England) with a load cell capacity of 5000N, crosshead speed of 50 mm/min.¹⁶

The notched Izod impact test was performed on a specimen with dimensions of 12.7 mm in width × 63.5 mm in length × 3.2 mm in thickness using an impact tester (Ceast, Resil Impactor 10K, USA) according to ASTM D256.¹⁷

The flexural test was conducted on a rectangular-shaped specimen with dimensions of 12.7 mm in width × 127 mm in length × 3.2 mm in thickness using a universal testing machine (Tinius Olsen, England) under three-point bending mode according to ASTM D790 with a load cell capacity of 5000N, crosshead speed of 5 mm/min, and support span length of 50 mm.¹⁸

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Polyester resin matrix reinforced with agro-waste fiber has shown impact toughness and strength results. Scrap wood as reinforcement provides superior mechanical properties compared to macadamia nutshells, rice husks, tea leaves, and coffee chaff. (Figure 3, Table 1). Additionally, flame spread testing demonstrated that BERD, composed of macadamia and tea leaf, did not spread flames (Table 2). It could be explained that lignin in macadamia and tannin in tea leaf tannin, act as flame-retardant components.^{19,20} While other agro-wastes lack of such properties. Several factors, however may influence the material testing results, including chemical composition, microstructure such as size, shape, and distribution of waste particles, layer arrangement, and aspect ratio.

Figure 3. Flexural strength testing (MOR, MPa)

Table 1. Results of mechanical properties testing of BERD containing different types of agro-waste as fillers.

Test	Coffee chaff	Tea leaves	Macadamia	Rice husks	Scrap wood
Tensile strength (MPa)					
average	7.09	5.38	12.45	7.10	15.20
SD	1.08	1.05	2.13	2.47	1.79
max	8.24	6.35	14.89	10.07	16.72
min	5.74	3.37	9.36	2.98	12.30
Impact strength (J/m ²)					
average	1207.49	1200.17	1130.98	925.93	1394.94
SD	147.80	139.56	151.75	223.11	446.43
max	1372.54	1388.10	1321.52	1162.01	2292.95
min	1008.47	1066.29	826.44	536.11	846.37
Flexural (MOR, MPa)					
average	24.06	24.72	28.91	30.58	40.24
SD	3.70	4.21	2.47	8.94	3.85
max	29.19	30.52	31.60	46.06	45.19
min	19.73	17.54	24.10	19.83	33.64

Table 2. Results of flame spread testing of BERD containing different types of agro-waste as fillers.

Test	Coffee chaff	Tea leaves	Macadamia	Rice husks	Scrap wood
Vertical Burning Rate (mins/5 cm.)	13.08	-	-	15.09	12.18

During the preparation of BERD composites, the moisture content and particle size of the agro-waste fillers were controlled to maintain consistent processing conditions. These factors are known to influence composite performance. For instance, excess moisture can interfere with resin curing and weaken the bonding between the filler and matrix. Similarly, fillers that are too coarse or uneven in size may lead to poor dispersion, surface imperfections, or a decline in mechanical strength.

The results also showed that scrap wood exhibits superior mechanical performance in composites due to its fibrous structure, which offers a high aspect ratio that enhances stress transfer between filler and matrix. The cellulose-rich fibers provide inherent stiffness, while the rough surface improves mechanical interlocking with the resin. These fibers also act as crack arresters, distributing load and increasing toughness. Compared to granular fillers, scrap wood forms a more effective reinforcing network, especially when well-dispersed. Additionally, its lignocellulosic composition contributes to both strength and energy absorption, making it an ideal filler for improving tensile, flexural, and impact resistance in bio-composites.

The properties of BERD composites were considered alongside those of synthetic stone materials commonly used in the market, such as engineered quartz and solid surface products. These conventional materials typically depend on petrochemical-based binders and non-renewable mineral fillers, which can pose environmental drawbacks. Natural stones like basalt and granite typically show tensile strengths of 10–25 MPa, depending on composition and testing methods.²¹ Engineered quartz-resin composites typically exhibit tensile strengths of 15–20 MPa and flexural strengths of 30–35 MPa, depending on filler content and resin type²², while impact strength is not a fixed value, as it varies significantly with composition and manufacturing process. However, this improved strength and durability often come at a higher production cost.

By contrast, BERD composites make use of agricultural waste, offering a more sustainable choice. In this study, certain formulations demonstrated impact strength comparable to solid surface and engineered quartz (except for rice husk formulations), indicating its suitability for interior applications requiring impact resistance. In addition, BERD composite offers strong durability over time due to the thermosetting resin's cross-linked structure, resisting deformation, moisture, and heat for over 15 years in interior applications. However, the resin is not biodegradable and may degrade under prolonged UV or chemical exposure, though this can be reduced with protective coatings. Using agro-waste fillers lowers the overall environmental impact.

While BERD delivers clear environmental benefits, its economic feasibility also enhances its potential for industrial adoption. Compared to natural rock, BERD uses low-cost agricultural waste and simplified composite processing, making it more affordable to produce and resulting in a lower cost per square meter. Its lighter weight reduces transportation and installation effort, while its customizable size and shape help minimize material waste. In addition, BERD's built-in fire and moisture resistance lowers long-term maintenance needs. When factoring in production efficiency, material savings, and lifecycle performance, BERD emerges as a cost-effective and sustainable alternative to natural stone in both commercial and residential applications.

Moving from lab-scale to industrial-scale production of BERD composites could come with a number of practical issues. Since agro-waste materials can vary depending on where and when they are sourced, things like moisture content, particle size, and composition might not always be consistent. This could affect the quality of the final product. To deal with that, standard steps for preparing and checking the raw materials would be important. In addition, scaling up might require adjusting mixing and molding equipment to keep the material uniform. The curing process especially how long it takes and at what temperature, may also need to be changed for bigger batches. For these reasons, running some pilot-scale tests before trying to mass-produce the composites would be a necessary step.

Figure 4. Material applications from BERD green composites

4. CONCLUSIONS

The Bio-Eco Rock Development (BERD), which utilizes agro-wastes as fillers, is an innovative upcycled green composite. Material property testing has demonstrated that the polyester resin matrix reinforced with agro-waste fibers exhibits favorable impact toughness and strength results. Consequently, BERD possesses unique qualities in terms of durability and practical applicability across various material domains (Figure 4). In conclusion, BERD contributes to the green circular economy by transforming waste into a valuable resource, addressing environmental challenges, and fostering a sustainable future.

5. AUTHOR INFORMATION

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Author Contributions

T.T. conducted the experiments, data analysis, and drafting of the manuscript; A.T. and P.V. conducted the experiments; A.B. conducted data analysis, and drafting of the manuscript; K.N. contributed to the conception, design, data analysis, and drafting of the manuscript.

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